

Feasible Traits of TV and Web as Media for Advertisements and Their Influences on Buying Behavior— A Comparative Study on Indian Perspective

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Abstract—Advertising is one of the important marketing strategies and the choice of media is an important aspect of effectiveness of advertising media. The two most popular advertising media, TV and web media are highly effective in creating successful advertisements as they influence the purchase decision of the viewers. Although TV and web are electronic media, they are unique in their features and traits of advertising. Hence, the present study attempts to analyze the influence of these two media towards buying behavior of the viewers. The two media are analyzed separately to determine its level of influence towards buying behavior and finally a comparative analysis of these media is attempted to find the difference in their level of influence.

Keywords—Buying Behavior, TV, web, media for advertisements.

I. INTRODUCTION

ADVERTISING is an inseparable aspect of product promotion. As a promotional strategy, advertising serves as a major tool in creating product awareness and persuades the potential consumers to take eventual purchase decisions [1]. The major element of advertising strategy is media selection for advertisement. Media are the means or vehicle by which advertising messages are carried to the target audience comprising of the readers, viewers, listeners and users of newspapers, television, radio and web respectively. They provide the channel of communications to take the messages to the right place, at the right time, to the right kind of people—the target audience. The effectiveness of an advertising media can be sustained by high level of its reachability, low cost, easy accessibility, and the use of audio-visual effect in presenting the advertisements. In the case of typical marketing situation, this may be increase in the sales or market share or penetration into a new market segment [2]. Television is a mass media of communication and entertainment, which makes it possible to reach a large number of audiences. Doordarshan claims to have its terrestrial reach to 70 million

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households in India, including rural areas. It is estimated that over 191 million television viewers are in urban areas and 171 million viewers are located in rural areas. In villages with a population between 1000 and 5,000, the average time spent in viewing television ranges between 24.6 to 32.0 minutes per working day. The same in metros and cities ranges between 32.1 to 36.8 minutes per working day. Cable and satellite channels reach 20 million homes mostly in urban [3]. On the other hand, World Wide Web, the most popular commercial component of internet is currently being used for a variety of purposes [4]. Hence, the present study investigates about the traits of TV and web media in influencing buying behavior.

II. METHODOLOGY

It was decided that a comparative study using primary data would be appropriate to investigate the objectives and the hypotheses. The instrument used to collect the data was a questionnaire. The data used for the purpose of this study were collected for a period of one year from 1st June 2011 to 31st May 2012. The researcher has presented and interpreted the collected data supported by quantitative techniques.

A. Statement of the Problem

The ultimate aim of advertising is to inform, to persuade and to remind about the brand/product advertised. The most important aspect being to persuade the viewers to buy the product decides the effectiveness of advertisements and the advertising media. Among, the types of media for advertisement ranging from banner and balloons to online and mobile advertising, the two popular electronic media viz., TV and website has wide audience in this information technology era. Hence, the research problem was framed to answer the following research questions:

- How successful is TV media in influencing the buying behavior of the viewers?
- Is web media is feasible in influencing the buying behavior of the viewers?
- Are TV and web both equally influence the buying behavior of the viewers?

B. Objectives of the Study

- To determine the traits of TV media that influences the buying behavior
- To determine the traits of web media that influences the buying behavior
- To compare the influences of TV and web media for advertisements towards buying behavior

C. Validity Test

The questionnaire was subjected to face and content validity whose determination was judgemental. There are two schools of thought on the distinctiveness of face and content validity. The first one saw face validity as just an indirect approach to the measurement of content validity [5], [6] whereas the second one treated them as separate and different tests [7], [8]. In this study, the researcher has subscribed to the second perspective where quantitative assessment of the content validity has been followed. The content validity on the traits of TV and web media influencing buying behavior is presented in Table I.

TABLE I
CONTENT VALIDITY RATIO FOR THE DESCRIPTION ON TV AND WEB AS MEDIA FOR ADVERTISEMENTS

S. No.	Statements	CVR
1.	Able to get accurate information	1.00
2.	Able to get information consistently	0.75
3.	Dependable with minimum downtime	0.75
4.	Content is up-to-date and accurate	1.00
5.	Look and feel is viewer friendly	1.00
6.	Fast and reliable	1.00
7.	Easy access	1.00
8.	Supportive to draw conclusions about the product/brand	0.50
9.	Suggestive to decide on the product/brand	1.00
10.	Credible Information	1.00
11.	Secure	1.00
12.	Allows users to inspire trust	0.75
13.	Allows users to acquire confidence	0.75
14.	Content is appropriate	1.00
15.	Communication provides individual attention to viewers	1.00
16.	Content is easy to understand	1.00
17.	Convenience of operating / viewing hours	1.00
18.	Information is found with minimum effort	0.50
19.	Visuals are appealing	1.00
20.	This media increases my confidence level	1.00

D. Pilot Study

After finalizing the number of items in the research instrument using face and content validity tests, a pilot study was undertaken for the following reasons:

- To assess the reliability of the items included under perception on TV and web as media for advertisements and the perception on the advertisements released in TV and web media.
- To ascertain the time taken to complete the questionnaire by the respondents.

E. Sampling Technique

The geographical area of Coimbatore with Tamil Nadu state of India was chosen as the Universe. The main reason for choosing Coimbatore District is that it is completely urbanized with increasing number of Internet users. The questionnaire was administered in person randomly to a majority of

respondents in the study area after oral confirmation that they are the audience for both the media under study. Also, Snowball Sampling Technique was used to collect data from respondents who are stationed far away from the researcher. On this basis the questionnaire was administered to 1500 respondents with a yielding rate of 77.1% (1001 usable questionnaires) since few questionnaires were not returned and a few were unusable and incomplete.

F. Statistical Tools for Analysis

The techniques used for analysis are multiple regression analysis and paired samples 't' test.

III. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The data for the present study collected from the respondents through questionnaire were tabulated and analyzed using appropriate statistical techniques mentioned in the research methodology. The results from the statistical analysis and corresponding interpretations of the objective-wise analysis of the study are presented in this section. All the numerical results of the percentage analysis are rounded off to the first significant digit.

Objective 1: Analysis on the Traits of TV Media that Influence the Buying Behavior of the Respondents

To study the factors that influence the buying behavior of the respondents after seeing advertisements in TV, the researcher has conducted multiple regression analysis. The independent variables are the items that captured the opinion of the respondents about advertisements in TV and the dependent variable is the buying behavior of the respondents after seeing advertisements in TV. The composite mean of the items that captured the buying behavior was taken as the data for the dependent variable. The test of significance was conducted with the following null and alternative hypotheses:

- H0. There is no significant relationship between the respondents' perception on TV media and their buying behavior
- H1. There is a significant relationship between the respondents' perception on TV media and their buying behavior

TABLE II
REGRESSION COEFFICIENTS FOR THE TRAITS OF TV MEDIA THAT INFLUENCES THE BUYING BEHAVIOR OF THE RESPONDENTS

S. No.	Items	β	t	Sig. at 5% level
1.	(Constant)	-	9.91	0.000
2.	Able to get accurate information	1.918	15.21	0.000
3.	Able to get information consistently	0.803	-3.38	0.001
4.	Dependable with minimum downtime	-0.607	6.17	0.000
5.	Content is up-to-date and accurate	0.106	4.71	0.000
6.	Look and feel is viewer friendly	0.077	0.16	0.874
7.	Fast and reliable	0.003	1.31	0.190
8.	Easy access	0.023	-0.78	0.434
9.	Supportive to draw conclusions about the product/brand	-0.014	0.90	0.367
10.	Suggestive to decide on the product/brand	0.016	-0.55	0.581
11.	Credible Information	-0.010	0.18	0.861
12.	Secure	0.003	0.04	0.972

13.	Allows users to inspire trust	0.001	-0.19	0.899
14.	Allows users to acquire confidence	-0.002	0.89	0.374
15.	Content is appropriate	0.015	-0.80	0.424
16.	Communication provides individual attention to viewers	-0.014	2.23	0.026
17.	Content is easy to understand	0.040	0.30	0.766
18.	Convenience of operating / viewing hours	0.005	2.55	0.011
19.	Information is found with minimum effort	0.046	-0.58	0.563
20.	Visuals are appealing	0.010	2.43	0.015
21.	This media increases my confidence level	0.043	2.89	0.004

β = Standardized Co-efficient; $t=t'$ value; $R^2=0.353$; Adjusted $R^2=0.340$; $F=26.683$

Table II shows the results of multiple regression analysis. $R^2=0.353$ and adjusted $R^2=0.340$. This means that 34% of the total variance in the dependent variable is explained by the independent variables. $F=26.683$ which is significant at 0.05 level. This means that the model is fit. On examination of the coefficient table it is found that the item, "Able to get accurate information" ($\beta=1.918$; $p=0.000$) is the strongest predictor for the buying behavior of the respondents followed by "Able to get information consistently" ($\beta=0.803$; $p=0.001$); "Dependable with minimum downtime" ($\beta=-0.067$; $p=0.000$); "Content is up-to-date and accurate" ($\beta=0.106$; $p=0.000$); "This media increases my confidence level" ($\beta=0.043$; $p=0.004$); "Visuals are appealing" ($\beta=0.010$; $p=0.015$); "Convenience of operating/viewing hours" ($\beta=0.005$; $p=0.011$); "Communication provides individual attention to viewers" ($\beta=-0.014$; $p=0.026$). All these items differ significantly among the respondents. Hence, H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted for the above variables. However, the other variables do not have a significant influence on the buying behavior of the respondents.

Objective 2: Analysis on the Traits of Web Media that Influences the Buying Behavior of the Respondents

To analyze the factors that influence the buying behavior of the respondents after seeing advertisements in the web, multiple regression analysis was conducted. The independent variables are the items that captured the opinion of the respondents about advertisements in the web and the dependent variable is the buying behavior of the respondents after seeing advertisements in the web. The composite mean of the items that captured the buying behavior was taken as the data for the dependent variable. To test for significant difference, the following hypotheses are framed:

- H0. There is no significant relationship between the respondents' perception on web media and their buying behavior
H1. There is a significant relationship between the respondents' perception on web media and their buying behavior

TABLE III
REGRESSION COEFFICIENTS FOR THE TRAITS OF WEB MEDIA THAT INFLUENCES THE BUYING BEHAVIOR OF THE RESPONDENTS

S. No.	Items	β	t	Sig. at 5% level
1.	(Constant)	-	12.538	0.000
2.	Able to get accurate information	-	-0.896	0.371
		0.025		
3.	Able to get information consistently	0.747	16.580	0.000
4.	Dependable with minimum downtime	0.451	5.304	0.000
5.	Content is up-to-date and accurate	0.351	4.644	0.000
6.	Look and feel is viewer friendly	-	-1.512	0.131
		0.042		
7.	Fast and reliable	0.004	0.139	0.889
8.	Easy access	0.044	1.553	0.121
9.	Supportive to draw conclusions about the product/brand	-	-0.314	0.753
		0.009		
10.	Suggestive to decide on the product/brand	0.019	0.693	0.488
11.	Credible Information	0.178	2.357	0.019
12.	Secure	0.009	0.332	0.740
13.	Allows users to inspire trust	0.051	1.872	0.061
14.	Allows users to acquire confidence	-	-0.256	0.798
		0.007		
15.	Content is appropriate	0.055	2.009	0.045
16.	Communication provides individual attention to viewers	-	-0.864	0.388
		0.023		
17.	Content is easy to understand	-	-0.534	0.594
		0.015		
18.	Convenience of operating / viewing hours	0.034	1.204	0.229
19.	Information is found with minimum effort	0.009	0.318	0.750
20.	Visuals are appealing	0.027	0.964	0.335
21.	This media increases my confidence level	0.042	1.561	0.119

β = Standardized Co-efficient; $t=t'$ value; $R^2=0.435$; Adjusted $R^2=0.424$; $F=37.755$.

Table III illustrates the results of multiple regression analysis. $R^2=0.435$ and adjusted $R^2=0.424$. This means that 42.4% of the total variance in the dependent variable is explained by the independent variables. $F= 37.755$ which is significant at 0.05 level. This means that the model is fit. On examination of the coefficient table it is found that the item, "Able to get information consistently" ($\beta=0.747$; $p=0.000$); "Dependable with minimum downtime" ($\beta=0.451$; $p=0.000$); "Content is up-to-date and accurate" ($\beta=0.351$; $p=0.000$); "Credible Information" ($\beta=0.178$; $p=0.019$); "Content is appropriate" ($\beta=0.055$; $p=0.045$), have an influence on the respondents' buying behavior after seeing advertisements in web. Hence, H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted for the above variables. However, the other variables do not have a significant influence on the buying behavior of the respondents.

Objective 3: Comparative Analysis on the Influence of TV and Web as Media for Advertisements towards the Respondents' Buying Behavior

To compare the influence of TV and web media over the buying behavior of the respondents, paired samples 't' test was conducted. The appropriate null and alternative hypotheses are:

- H1. There is no significant difference in the buying behavior of the respondents after seeing advertisements in TV and web.

H2. There is a significant difference in the buying behavior of the respondents after seeing advertisements in TV and web.

TABLE IV
 PAIRED SAMPLES T-TEST FOR THE BUYING BEHAVIOR OF THE RESPONDENTS
 AFTER SEEING ADVERTISEMENTS IN TV AND WEB MEDIA

	Description	MD	SD	t	Sig. (2 tailed)
Pair 1	Buying behavior after seeing advertisements in TV				
	Buying behavior after seeing advertisements in web	0.21	1.222	5.395	0.000

MD- Mean difference; SD-Standard Deviation; t = 't' Test Value; Degrees of freedom=1000.

Table IV shows that there is a significant difference ($t=5.395$; $p=0.000$) in the buying behavior of the respondents after seeing advertisements in TV and web media. Hence, H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted at 5% level of significance. The buying behavior of the respondents after seeing an advertisement in TV (mean=5.08) is higher than that of web (mean=4.87). The mean difference = 0.21. Finally, the paired sample statistics is presented in Table V.

TABLE V
 PAIRED SAMPLES STATISTICS FOR THE BUYING BEHAVIORS OF THE
 RESPONDENTS AFTER SEEING ADVERTISEMENTS IN TV AND WEB MEDIA

	Description	Mean	SD
Pair 1	Buying behavior after seeing advertisements in TV	5.08	1.09
	Buying behavior after seeing advertisements in web	4.87	1.20

SD- Standard Deviation; N=1001

IV. IMPLICATIONS

- Although various traits of TV media influence the buying behavior of the respondents, the coefficients imply that the level of influence is very less in almost all factors. Hence, it is suggested that both TV and web media should incorporate more features to induce buying behavior.
- On the other hand, both TV and web media should enhance its features for a more viewer-friendly look which is fast and reliable and can be easily accessed.
- The content in TV and web media do not entrust confidence, security and trust among the respondents and it does not allow drawing conclusions about the product. Measures should be taken to instill trust and confidence about the media. Also, the content in both these media are not appropriate and cannot be understood easily which diminishes the influence towards buying behavior. It is suggested to create easily understandable and appropriate content in these media.
- It is suggested that the visuals in the web media should be appealing and provide accurate information which will enhance confidence level.
- It is suggested that credible information should be created in TV media to influence the buying behavior.

V. CONCLUSION

The present study with the aim of analyzing the traits of TV and web media to influence the buying behavior has implied that, both these media are not completely successfully. Although previous works are done with the advertisements in knowing its influence in buying behavior, this paper has attempted to analyze the media as a whole rather than the common factor advertisements. It is clear from the study that TV media has its own features to induce buying behavior and web media has its unique features to induce buying behavior. But it is strongly recommended that both the media needs much more attention to influence the buying behavior completely.

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